

Data Sharing Policy Development Guidelines

Australian Research Data Commons

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Document Purpose

This document provides information and guidance on the ‘how’ and ‘what’ of developing a data sharing policy (DSP).

Data sharing can be a component of good data management for enhancing research, and it relies on a data sharing policy that governs the access and reuse of the data. This document discusses the development of the principles forming a data sharing policy.

A data sharing policy can be part of the data governance framework for a research project as it supports components of data access, which is a fundamental part of data governance.

What Is a Data Sharing Policy?

A data sharing policy is a policy written by an organisation or a group that addresses:

- the types of data the agencies have in their custody
- the principles and strategy around the sharing of that data
- the governance and management procedures that should be followed when that data is being shared.

It lays out, in general terms, how that organisation or group will respond to requests to share the data.

To avoid confusion, it is important to consider how this differs from a data sharing agreement. A data sharing agreement is a formal agreement between a data provider and a data requester that refers to a specific case of data sharing. It typically takes the form of a binding contract between the two parties, and it clearly documents the terms and conditions under which the data are being shared.

When a data sharing request is made, the provider’s data sharing policy will inform the process by which the provider receives the request, how and by whom the request is assessed, and the conditions under which the provider is willing to make the data available. These conditions will be reflected in the data sharing agreement between the data provider and the data requester. A data sharing agreement can therefore be seen to instantiate the data provider’s data sharing policy.

The data sharing policy along with data sharing agreement guidance documentation should be referenced in any data governance policy, guidance, or requirements documents that are written. Additionally, data sharing is an important component of the research data management lifecycle. It needs to be considered and commented on during the development of a data management plan (DMP).

When writing a DMP, ensure you have a data sharing policy in place that comments on how the data created from the research project can be shared.

When Is a Data Sharing Policy Required?

A data sharing policy should be agreed on whenever there is a need or an intention to share data created by a research project or projects. The policy ensures that all data requests are handled consistently and appropriately. It also ensures that both the data holder and potential data requesters understand the process of making and assessing requests.

Depending on the requirements of the data holder, the policy might be made at the level of the organisation, the research group or a specific project or dataset. It may be the case that while a larger group or organisation typically follows a set of principles and processes for data sharing, certain datasets require more complex governance requirements or sharing conditions. In this case, a standard template for a data sharing policy can be created and then modified as needed to fit the specifics of individual research projects or data to be shared or accessed.

How to Create or Set Up a Data Sharing Policy

Firstly, determine if your organisation or institution has existing templates for developing policy documents. If so, use the template to create the policy. If not, it will be necessary to work and liaise with your legal department and/or research office to create the policy. If there are multiple stakeholders in the project, ensure they are aware of the data sharing policy and agree on the terms. Also, conversations should be held with those requesting to reuse the data to ensure they are aware of the principles being included in the policy.

It is important to review the potential components of a data sharing policy and determine which components should be included in the policy document being created. The components are described below.

Common Components of a Data Sharing Policy

The following are the key components that should be included in a data sharing policy.

Regulatory requirements

There may be other legislative, funder or institutional policies impacting the handling and sharing of data that need to be referenced and commented on as part of the data sharing policy. Examples include:

- privacy legislation
- [the National Statement on Ethical Conduct in Human Research](#)
- [the Australian Code for the Responsible Conduct of Research](#)
- institutional intellectual property policy
- funder's policy
- institutional or organisational data management and data governance policies.

These additional policies can be commented on. It is also important to provide any links to the policies so they can be referred to.

Data governance requirements

Specific governance requirements related to the sharing of data may need to be stated in the policy. If your institution or organisation has a data governance framework or policy, a link to this document can be included in the data sharing policy. If not, consider covering the following points in the policy:

- ethical concerns related to the data, such as ethics approval for handling human, animal or Indigenous data
- consent
- participant confidentiality
- rights of or reporting obligations to:
 - participants (with regard to incidental findings, use of data, etc.)
 - custodians
 - institutions
 - requesters
- roles and responsibilities.

Procedures for accessing and reusing the data

The following areas need to be considered, discussed and potentially included in the data sharing policy. They are associated with accessing and reusing the data.

- **Permitted uses**

Comment on what the data can and cannot be used for. For instance, the data could be used for further research but not commercial purposes.

- **Application and review process**

Provide details on how a data requester can apply to access the data, who they need to contact, an EOI process. Comment on the steps involved in reviewing applications, who will undertake the review and key elements they will be looking for, such as detailed reasoning for accessing the data and clear reuse requirements.

- **Timeframes and costs**

How long will it take to respond to a data request? Specify the number of days the turnaround will take (e.g. 30 days). Also comment on whether there are any costs associated with sharing the data.

- **Data handling and security**

Depending on the sensitivity of the data, there might be specific processes in place for the handling of the data, which might influence the sharing of the data. For instance, demographic data may need to be deidentified. Also, cybersecurity measures may need to be employed to further protect the data.

- **Publishing and releasing findings**

How the data will be released to the requester needs to be described. Comment on the formats and tools that will be used to enable access to the data. The data may also have been published and be made accessible that way.

- **Reuse requirements**

The policy needs to ensure there is an understanding as to why the data is being accessed and how it is to be reused. This will inform requests for reusing the data and whether they are likely to be approved. Areas that should be considered are:

- reasons for accessing the data
- purposes of reuse
- potential risks involved in the reuse of the data
- retention of the data after access has been granted
- continued use of the data, future developments.

- **Data sharing agreement**

It may be necessary to comment on the development and application of a data sharing agreement, which will dictate the terms and conditions and governance for the sharing of the data. Refer to the ARDC's [Data Sharing Agreements Guidelines](#) for support.

- **Updates to approved requests**

It might be the case that after a request is submitted, changes need to be made. A change management process is required for recording these requests. Also, updates to the future use of the data might be required once the data has been shared. A process needs to be in place to allow the data requester to inform the provider that circumstances of use have changed, and vice versa.

- **Managing misuse of the data**

In the case of data misuse, a change management process enables any changes in use to be recorded. Data misuse is a risk that needs to be mentioned in the policy.

- **Review of progress**

Comments on how the request for data is progressing should be documented. Standard text used to update the data requester should be formulated.

Licensing

A licence or data sharing agreement will stipulate the potential reuse and access conditions for the data that is being shared. Agreeing on a licence or laying out the steps to determine the licence to apply is a fundamental component of a data sharing policy. Aspects to consider include:

- acknowledgement and attribution – see for example attribution in [Creative Commons licensing](#)
- data sharing agreements
- any conditions applied by the author on the data
- intellectual property and copyright
- publication or on-provision of data.

Change management

With the development of any policy, it is important to document management procedures regarding changes (in this case, changes to data requests or updates to the policy document) so that they can be recorded and subsequently audited. It is important to consider the following questions in the data sharing policy when it comes to change management:

- How will changes be recorded and documented?

- Who is authorised to approve changes associated to data sharing?
- Should a new access request be made or can amendments be made to existing requests?
- How can changes be tracked and the process monitored?

Technical framework

It is important to consider and record any technologies that might impact the sharing of data in the policy.

- What technology and/or systems or tools will be used to assist the sharing of and access to the data?
- Management and maintenance of technologies
- Are there any technical considerations that need to be adhered to in relation to the sharing of the data?

Data classification

A very important component for understanding the data in a project is its classification. The data might be sensitive or have specific criteria attached to it that might impact its ability to be shared. Such issues need to be described in the policy.

- Is the data classified as sensitive? If so, what procedures are in place for handling the data?
- Is the data publicly available? Are there restrictions and terms of use that need to be adhered to before the data can be shared?
- What tools or systems are employed to support the handling of the data (especially if it's sensitive data)?
- Does access to the data need to be mediated?

Understanding these components is key to formulating the terms and conditions of the data sharing policy.

Summary

This document gives guidance on the components that should or could be included in the development of a data sharing policy. A data sharing policy covers more ground than a data sharing agreement, which is a legal document signed between the parties wanting to share or access the data. A data sharing policy covers such aspects as data governance, access conditions, rights and technology.

The table below lists and explains the components to be included in the data sharing policy:

Component	Explanation
Regulatory requirements	Provide details of any other policies that might influence the sharing of the data, such as privacy legislation, funder requirements and data management policies.
Data governance	What governance has been applied to the data? Comment on the ethics and the roles and responsibilities when it comes to sharing the data.
Procedures for accessing and reusing the data	<p>How will the data be accessed and shared? Detail the process of making an access request, the steps involved and any documentation.</p> <p>It is important to document and understand the reason why the data is being requested and the reasons for reuse. Risks associated with reusing the data should also be checked to ensure the data isn't misused. There may also be other constraints added to the data that will influence the extent to which the data can be reused.</p>
Licencing	The application of a licence to the data being shared influences how it can be reused. Consider whether a licence is required or if a data sharing agreement with specific terms and conditions will be put in place.
Change management	During the access process, changes in the request might occur. These will need to be documented and handled accordingly by a change manager. Changes to the policy may also occur and will similarly need to be recorded.
Technical framework	It is important to understand any technology or systems that will be employed to facilitate the access and sharing of the data, such as the use of repositories or newly developed data management tools. It is also necessary to be able to capture the actual access requests and any documents or forms using a tool of some kind.
Data classification	Data classification influences the accessibility of the data. Sensitive data, for instance, will require additional consideration before it can be accessed and shared.

In addition to covering the components stated above in the policy, it is also important to include a preamble that states the purpose of the policy and what is in and out of its scope. You may also want to

include a glossary and links to other resources that complement and support the policy, such as a data governance framework and research data management policies.